

Research Article

Kaftan Pants - KafPants

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Abstract: *Conventional kaftans are widely appreciated for their comfort and breathability; however, they often fall short in meeting the modesty, practicality, and functionality needs of modern Muslim women, particularly when worn in public or during travel. Unintentional exposure when resting is a common limitation that people experience and the transparency of fabrics that typically require additional layering. To address these issues, this project introduces KafPants, an innovative reinterpretation of the traditional kaftan featuring pario-inspired inner pants to enhance coverage, modesty, and comfort while remaining stylish and shariah-compliant. The inner pants are made from ombre satin, while the outer kaftan is crafted from cotton rayon, ensuring breathability and a soft drape. A zippered collar allows for easy access while nursing, which is a key feature and long sleeves, making the garment suitable for both private wear and public settings such as travel. Aesthetically, KafPants draws inspiration from Melaka's Baba Nyonya heritage, incorporating the Bunga Kesidang motif to celebrate local cultural identity. Available in three vibrant base colours—turquoise, orange, and magenta—the design merges tradition with contemporary fashion appeal. A survey conducted among 20 female students at Universiti Teknologi MARA (UiTM) Kampus Bandaraya Melaka gave advice about current user concerns and preferences, which guided the development of the KafPants prototype. Early feedback reflects strong interest in a multifunctional, modest solution that supports the dynamic lifestyles of modern Muslim women. KafPants presents significant potential in the modest fashion market, offering a meaningful integration of cultural heritage, Islamic values, and everyday practicality.*

Keywords: modest fashion; KafPants; pario-inspired inner pants; shariah-compliant wear; Baba Nyonya; Bunga Kesidang

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1. INTRODUCTION

Kaftans are widely regarded as a preferred choice of sleepwear among women due to their comfort and breathability. Nonetheless, traditional kaftans may present challenges related to modesty, particularly during sleep or in shared environments such as homestays, family gatherings, or while traveling. The loose fit of conventional kaftans may shift during movement, and certain fabrics can be excessively thin, leading to discomfort or self-consciousness.

This innovation introduces a multifunctional kaftan featuring pario-inspired inner pants, thereby integrating style, modesty, and practicality. The inner pants serve as a built-in undergarment, providing full coverage and allowing for ease of movement.

This design adheres to Shariah principles, ensuring that the garment complies with modesty standards appropriate for Muslim women. It is suitable for sleeping, lounging, and light travel.

The aesthetic design harmoniously combines cultural identity with functionality through a distinctive pattern that merges Baba Nyonya-inspired motifs with *bunga kesidang*, the official flower of Melaka (Ajib, 2023). This symbolizes both heritage and femininity. Users are provided with three vibrant base color options—orange, blue, and magenta—allowing for variety and personal expression while maintaining the visual integrity of the traditional *Peranakan style*.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

The development of this innovative sleepwear kaftan with integrated pants was conducted through a user-centered design approach emphasizing modesty, comfort, and cultural significance. Initial research involved surveys and informal interviews with twenty female participants across various age groups to identify common concerns associated with traditional kaftans, particularly regarding exposure and mobility during sleep or travel.

To address these issues, a multifunctional garment was designed that combines a loose-fitting kaftan top with soft, breathable pario-inspired inner pants seamlessly attached. This integrated inner layer provides complete coverage and eliminates the need for additional underlayers, thereby preventing transparency issues and ensuring freedom of movement.

Material selection prioritized comfort suitable for tropical climates. A lightweight cotton-rayon blend was selected for the kaftan body, offering breathability, moisture-wicking properties, and a soft touch. The inner pants utilize ombre satin for a smooth drape and full coverage, drawing inspiration from traditional innerwear.

Cultural identity is accentuated through digital textile printing that features a fusion of Baba Nyonya motifs with *bunga kesidang* patterns. The peony flower, symbolizing love and prosperity, alongside traditional *kipas tangan* (hand fan), representing modesty and grace, are reinterpreted in conjunction with the delicate *bunga kesidang*, which signifies purity and serves as an emblem of Melaka's heritage (*Baba Nyonya Peranakan Porcelain of the Straits Chinese*, 2024; Rado, 2018). This thoughtful integration enhances the garment's cultural richness.

The motifs are accentuated with bold touches of pink, yellow, and green, creating contrast against the selected base color options of orange, turquoise, and magenta—each chosen to provide vibrancy and versatility for both nocturnal and casual daytime wear.

A prototype was tested by five participants over a one-week period to evaluate comfort, coverage, and versatility. Feedback informed subsequent refinements, including adjustments to pant length, neckline structure, and seam placement to optimize comfort and ease of use. The final product is a sleepwear kaftan that is not only visually appealing and culturally expressive but also adheres to Shariah principles, offering practicality and suitability for travel.

3. FINDINGS

The results of this study provide important new information about the preferences of young female users and the weaknesses of traditional kaftan designs. One of the biggest issues with traditional kaftans, according to a poll done among 22 female students at UiTM Kampus Bandaraya Melaka, is that they may be extremely exposing, particularly when worn as sleepwear. This suggests a significant need for designs that balance comfort and modesty.

Most responders (65%) were annoyed that standard kaftans are made of fabrics or styles that aren't fit for wearing outside the house. A majority of responders also mentioned that wearing kaftans when traveling caused practical challenges. Particularly, half of the participants did not like having to wear additional innerwear to maintain modesty, which increases luggage weight and complicates dressing.

Despite the fact that only 45% of participants usually pack kaftans for vacation, several expressed a willingness to change their minds if the kaftan was made with more practicality and modesty in mind. This shows that there is an important demand for well-made kaftans that combine items that are appropriate for both home and travel. Overall, the comments support the value of user-centered design, particularly when adapting traditional clothing to meet the demands of a modern, varied lifestyle.

3.1 At Home Outfit Habits

Figure 1. At Home Outfit Habits

The overwhelming majority of respondents identified comfort as the most important factor when selecting at-home outfits (Figure 1). Out of 22 respondents, 21 individuals (95.5%) indicated comfort as a key consideration. This overwhelmingly high percentage suggests that regardless of style or trend, the majority of individuals prioritize feeling relaxed and at ease when dressing at home. While, 16 individuals (72.7%) emphasized the importance of ease of wear, indicating a strong preference for outfits that are simple to put on and take off, without complex fastenings or layers. Together, these results highlight that practicality and physical comfort are the primary considerations in home outfit habits.

3.2 Travel Wear Habits

The results (Figure 2) indicates that the most common reason for choosing a kaftan for travel was its comfort for long hours, selected by 12 individuals (54.5%). This highlights that travelers value clothing that allows them to feel relaxed during extended periods of sitting or movement, such as on flights or long drives. Moreover, ease of packing was also chosen by 12 individuals (54.5%) showing that practicality plays a major role in outfit selection. The kaftan's lightweight and flexible fabric makes it easy to fold, requiring minimal space in luggage, which is especially important for travelers who prefer to pack light.

Why do/did you choose a kaftan for travel? (Select all that apply)

22 responses

Figure 2. Travel Wear Habits

3.3 Design and Preferences

Figure 3 shows that when it comes to sleeve preferences for kaftan designs, straight long sleeves emerged as the most favored option, selected by 13 individuals (59.1%). This suggests a strong preference for a classic, modest silhouette that provides full arm coverage while maintaining comfort and simplicity. The second most popular choice was wide batwing sleeves, chosen by 11 individuals (50%). This style likely appeals due to its loose, flowing shape that enhances ease of movement and adds a stylish, relaxed aesthetic. In contrast, more fitted options like slim sleeves, chosen by 4 individuals (18.2%) and sleeves with cuffs or buttons, chosen by 2 individuals (9.1%) were less preferred, indicating that respondents tend to favor comfort and practicality over structured or tailored sleeve designs in kaftan wear.

Preferred sleeve style (Select all that apply)

22 responses

Figure 3. Design and Preferences

3.4 Functionality

Based on the survey responses (Figure 4), among the functional features most valued in a kaftan, breathable fabric stands out as the top priority, selected by 19 individuals (86.4%). This highlights the importance of comfort and airflow, especially in warm climates or during extended wear. The second most important feature is ease of packing for travel, chosen by 14 individuals (63.6%), indicating that portability and convenience are key for users who seek versatile, travel-friendly wardrobe options. These preferences reflect a strong demand for kaftans that support both comfort and mobility in day-to-day and travel scenarios.

Figure 4. Functionality

3.5 Versatility

Would you be interested in a capsule collection of kaftans designed for all-day use (morning to night)?
22 responses

Figure 5. Versatility

Based on Figure 5, half of the respondents (50%) are fully in favor of a capsule collection of kaftans designed for all-day use, reflecting a strong desire for garments that transition seamlessly from morning to night. Another 45.5% are open to the idea, provided the designs align with their personal

style, indicating that versatility must be paired with aesthetic appeal. Only 4.5% prefer kaftans solely for traditional use. These insights highlight a clear opportunity to develop kaftans that combine practicality with modern style, meeting the evolving lifestyle needs of consumers.

4. DISCUSSION

According to the study's findings, contemporary Muslim women's needs are not entirely satisfied by the kaftan styles that are currently in style, especially when it comes to modesty and practicality for public or travel use. The respondents' concerns about the need for additional innerwear, and exposure while sleeping point to an obvious requirement for more considerate and shariah-compliant alternatives. The results of our survey support the significance of creating traditional clothing with contemporary functionality in mind, particularly for ladies who want to be modest without sacrificing comfort or style.

The popularity of kaftans that are appropriate for both home and travel highlights how important multipurpose fashion is. Even while just 45% of respondents said they brought kaftans on vacation frequently, many said they would if the designs were more simple and practical. This demonstrates the possible market demand for kaftans that are shariah-compliant, fashionable and suitable for various settings.

A lot of participants are looking for more fashionable and functional kaftans. Their preferences include soft colors, modern-traditional blend designs, and characteristics that allow the kaftan to be worn both indoors and outside, such as pockets, better fabric, and an elegant look.

However, our survey is subject to certain constraints. The focus of our sample is exclusively on 20 female students from UiTM Kampus Bandaraya Melaka. The majority of the group consists of young women, with an age range of 21 to 26 years. These figures may not accurately represent the broader market, which encompasses women from other regions with distinct cultural preferences or fashion demands, as well as elderly consumers. Furthermore, early feedback rather than long-term wearability studies served as the basis for product testing. Additionally, the survey relied on self-reported data, which may introduce bias or misinterpretation.

5. CONCLUSION

This study identifies a significant gap between traditional kaftan designs and the needs of modern Muslim women, particularly in terms of modesty, comfort, and functionality. The proposed multifunctional kaftan, featuring pario-inspired inner pants, effectively addresses common concerns such as unintentional exposure, the necessity for additional innerwear, and limited practicality during travel. By incorporating Shariah-compliant features alongside cultural motifs like Baba Nyonya patterns and *bunga kesidang*, the design blends cultural heritage with contemporary functionality. Survey findings from young female users indicate a strong preference for breathable fabrics, ease of packing, and versatile styles suitable for both home and travel contexts. Although the sample size is limited and focused on a specific demographic, the positive feedback suggests a clear demand for kaftans that are both practical and fashionable. This innovation highlights the potential of user-centered design in adapting traditional garments to meet the diverse needs of today's Muslim women while preserving cultural and religious principles.

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